

ДИАЛОГ КАК КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЙ СПОСОБ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

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***Аннотация.** Диалог является одной из важнейших форм коммуникативного общения между людьми. Он представляет собой процесс взаимодействия, в ходе которого участники обмениваются информацией, мыслями и эмоциями. Диалог способствует установлению взаимопонимания и развитию социальных связей. В отличие от монолога, диалог основан на активном участии всех коммуникантов и предполагает обратную связь. Как форма коммуникативного общения, диалог характеризуется динамичностью и гибкостью. Участники диалога постоянно меняются ролями говорящего и слушающего. Это позволяет корректировать высказывания в зависимости от реакции собеседника. Благодаря этому информация передаётся более точно и эффективно. Диалогическая речь обычно носит ситуативный характер и зависит от контекста общения. Важную роль в диалоге играют не только вербальные, но и невербальные средства общения. Жесты, мимика, интонация и зрительный контакт усиливают смысл высказываний и помогают лучше понять намерения собеседника. Невербальные элементы особенно значимы в живом общении, так как они передают эмоциональное состояние участников диалога.*

Диалог широко используется в различных сферах человеческой деятельности. В образовательной среде он способствует активному усвоению знаний, в профессиональной сфере - эффективному взаимодействию между коллегами, а в социальной жизни - укреплению межличностных отношений. Таким образом, диалог как коммуникативное общение играет ключевую роль в развитии личности и общества в целом.

***Ключевые слова:** диалог, общение, коммуникация, дискурс, взаимодействие.*

DIALOGUE AS A COMMUNICATIVE COMMUNICATION

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In the contemporary system of the humanities, the problem of communication-particularly the theory of dialogue-emerges as one of the most relevant research directions. The rapid acceleration of globalization, the unprecedented expansion of information, the increasingly dynamic and interconnected nature of social and cul-tural processes, oblige a reconsideration of both the essence and the diverse forms of human interaction. Within this context, dialogue is no longer examined solely as a linguistic or literary category; rather, it has evolved into a multifaceted phenomenon explored at the intersection of multiple disciplines, including social psychology, phi-losophy, communication theory, and cultural studies. This interdisciplinary approach highlights dialogue not only as a methodological tool but as a fundamental aspect of understanding human relations, social structures, and cultural transformations.

Dialogue, as the oldest and simultaneously the most universal form of human communication, has played a fundamental role throughout history in regulating so-cial relations, transmitting knowledge and practical experience, shaping cultural and moral traditions. In ancient Greek philosophy, Socrates regarded dialogue as the principal method for acquiring knowledge, emphasizing that the development of human thought occurs within the context of dialogical interaction, where ideas are formed, challenged, and refined through reciprocal exchange. In modern social and humanitarian scholarship, M. Bakhtin's characterization of dialogue as the "funda-mental principle of thought and communication" has introduced new theoretical and scientific perspectives

on the concept of dialogue. According to Bakhtin, individuals establish their understanding of themselves and their relationship with the world through dialogue, thus, dialogue isn't only a form or technique of speech, but represents a mode of existence, a way of being in constant interaction with others and with the surrounding reality. In this sense, dialogue encompasses cognitive, ethical, and existential dimensions, highlighting its centrality not only in human communication but also in the very process of self-consciousness and social existence.

The communicative character of dialogue has become increasingly pronounced in XXI century. The advancement of information and communication technologies has extended dialogue beyond conventional physical spaces into virtual environments, digital platforms, and social networks, thereby engendering a novel communicative paradigm. Within these contexts, dialogue is conceptualized not only as the interaction between two individuals, but as a networked form of communication involving multiple participants. Accordingly, dialogue undergoes significant transformations in content, structure, and function, that put it as a critical subject of inquiry, within contemporary communication theory.

The exploring of dialogue, as a form of communicative interaction necessitates a comprehensive examination of multiple parameters, including its linguistic structure, semantic organization, pragmatic functions, dependence on social context, and the mechanisms governing participant interaction. Dialogue, in essence, isn't only an interaction mediated by language, it constitutes a complex, multilayered system in which social relationships, cultural codes, psychological states, contextual factors, social roles, and communicative strategies are manifested. Consequently, dialogue can be analyzed across multiple levels: as a textual entity, as a dynamic process, and as a system of interpersonal relations.

Dialogue, as a form of communicative interaction, is characterized by a number of distinctive features. Primarily, it is grounded in the principle of reciprocity, where, participants engage the exchange of information through speech acts directed toward one another, negotiate positions, share meanings, and establish both emotional and social connections. Unlike monologue, dialogue entails not only the transmission of information but the co-construction of meaning; that is, the ultimate significance of a communicative act emerges as a result of interactive engagement. This characteristic delineates the inherently interactive, dynamic, and structurally open nature of dialogue.

A fundamental characteristic of dialogue is its inherent situationality. Dialogic communication is invariably instantiated within a defined context, bounded by specific spatiotemporal parameters, and embedded within a network of social roles and relational structures. Variations in context apply a profound influence on the content of the dialogue, the selection and realization of speech acts, the modulation of illocutionary force, the articulation of semantic and pragmatic subtleties, and the strategic deployment of communicative behaviors. Accordingly, contextual factors occupy a central position in the analysis of dialogue, whole the primary object of investigation for understanding both its structural properties and its pragmatic functioning within social interaction.

Additionally, dialogue is pragmatically oriented. Its function extends over the only transfer of propositional content to encompass the negotiation of social understanding, the management of situational context, the regulation of affective relationships, the exertion of influence, and the facilitation of consensus. In this regard, dialogue can be conceptualized as a form of social conduct. Each instance of human interaction within a dialogic exchange involves both overt and covert pragmatic intentions, as well as the deployment of communicative strategies and tactics, thereby contributing to the structural and functional complexity of the dialogical system.

The exploring of dialogue as a communicative function, also necessitates an investigation into its linguistic nature. From a linguistic perspective, dialogue differs from monologue in terms of syntactic, lexical, intonational, and structural features. Typical characteristics of dialogue include a high frequency of short, elliptical, or incomplete sentences; the rapid succession of speech acts; emotionally intensified expressions; and the involvement of gestures, facial expressions, and other non-verbal means. These features have emerged as a consequence of dialogue adapting to the dynamics of live communication. The inclusion of non-verbal elements further enhances the

functionality and effectiveness of dialogue, since only a portion of communication is realized through language alone.

The researching of dialogue in the contemporary era holds significant importance from the perspective of intercultural communication. Dialogical interactions, that arise among representatives of different cultures are characterized not only by linguistic differences but also by the diversity of cultural codes, social norms, and models of ethical behavior. This necessitates the identification of the specific pragmatic and social features of intercultural dialogue. In a globalizing world, intercultural dialogue is considered one of the primary instruments for fostering values such as peace, cooperation, tolerance, and mutual understanding.

In general, dialogue, as a form of communicative interaction, is extensively employed across all domains of human society, encompassing education, political processes, psychology, organizational management, cultural practices, and everyday social life. In contemporary societal contexts, dialogue assumes a pivotal role not only in the resolution of conflicts and the facilitation of decision-making processes, but also in the mechanisms underpinning social integration, solidarity, and adaptive functioning. The communication paradigm grounded in dialogue is acknowledged, as one of the foundational principles of democratic governance and open, participatory societies. Consequently, the systematic and scholarly investigation of the theoretical underpinnings, communicative properties, and social functions of dialogue is of critical significance, bearing both theoretical importance and practical applicability across diverse social and institutional contexts.

Thus, dialogue, as a form of communicative interaction, has been conceptualized in contemporary scientific thought, as a complex, multifaceted, and multidisciplinary domain of inquiry. The systematic exploring of dialogue facilitates a profound understanding of human cognition, social relationships, mechanisms of language development, and intercultural communication processes. From this point of view, the scientific examination of dialogue holds not only theoretical significance, but also provides a critical methodological foundation for various practical applications. The topical relevance, extensive applicability, and theoretical import of the subject underscore the necessity and expediency of investigating dialogue as a distinct form of communicative interaction.

Dialogue has been explained as a means of communication from various perspectives by different scholars. In Saidov's book "*Theory of Communication*", communication is analyzed from multiple aspects. He evaluates the communication process not merely as the transmission of information, but also as a process of interaction, understanding, and the sharing of meaning. From this perspective, dialogue emerges as the central form of communicative interaction:

- dialogue is presented by the author as a form of communication that ensures the active participation of parties in the process of interaction and exchange of ideas.

- dialogue is not limited to the transmission of information; it also plays a role in creating understanding, relationships, and emotional connections among participants.

This perspective considers dialogue as "the process of direct and mutual interpretation of texts and symbols." In addition, Saidov emphasizes that dialogue differs from other forms of communication:

- difference from monologue: dialogue is not one-sided; it requires the active participation of two or more parties.

- mutual influence: in the process of dialogue, participants not only receive information but also influence the other party and respond.

- social function: dialogue also serves as a means for establishing and developing social relationships.

In contemporary linguistics, the exploring of communication has entered a new phase with the focus on the human factor. In this regard, E. S. Kubryakova's work "Man and His Language: Communication and Cognition" occupies an important place in the study of the relationships between language, thought, and interaction. In the scholar's approach, dialogue is presented as the primary and most natural form of communicative interaction.

According to Kubryakova, dialogue isn't only a process of information changing but also a complex cognitive activity. During dialogue, participants respond to each other's speech, construct meanings together, and exert mutual influence within the communication process. Therefore, dialogue isn't static; it has a dynamic character and is constantly developing.

Another researcher, A. Sternin, in the work "Foundations of Communicative Language Theory", presents dialogue as the primary means of communicative inter-action. According to the author, dialogue is not merely an exchange of speech or text, but also a process in which participants mutually shape each other's meanings, intentions, and social relations. That is, through dialogue, people not only exchange information but also establish social and emotional connections, making it a central element of communicative interaction.

But Brown and Yule consider dialogue as the primary form of human communication in their research. They emphasize, that speaking isn't only a process aimed at transmitting information, but also a dynamic activity that organizes social inter-action, creates meaning, and ensures mutual understanding. In other words, communication isn't only a written or formal structure, but also a primary means through which people establish relationships and share meaning within a social context.

Let us consider alternative perspectives. Deborah Tannen's "Talking Voices: Repetition, Dialogue, and Imagery in Conversational Discourse" represents a seminal exploring, that offers a novel approach to the concept of dialogic communication. In this work, the author examines everyday spoken language not only as a vehicle for information transfer, but as a primary mode of interaction through which social relationships are constituted and negotiated.

At last, conclusion is that, dialogue functions not as an exchange of information, but as a dynamic process through which social relationships, identities, and shared understanding are constructed and maintained. It highlights the inherently interactive and relational nature of human communication.

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